

Development of an RFID-Based Patient Identification System for Special Care Environments

Leoncio Perez Taucei
Federal Technological University of
Paraná
Curitiba, Paraná, Brazil
ORCID: 0009-0009-6411-9741

Adriana Aparecida Xavier
Federal Technological University of
Paraná
Curitiba, Paraná, Brazil
ORCID: 0009-0000-2835-2284

Felipe Cordeiro Sabatino
Federal Technological University of
Paraná
Curitiba, Paraná, Brazil
ORCID: 0009-0005-6533-4348

Felipe Barros Zagonel
Federal University of Paraná
Curitiba, Paraná, Brazil
ORCID: 0009-0004-8407-1021

Cristhiane Gonçalves
Federal Technological University of
Paraná – PPGEB-CT
Ponta Grossa, Paraná, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-3894-2971

Frieda Saicla Barros
Federal Technological University of
Paraná- PPGEB-CT
Curitiba, Paraná, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-1645-1111

Abstract — This paper describes the development of an innovative patient identification and monitoring system based on Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology, designed specifically for special care settings such as the Pequeno Cotelengo Healthcare Complex. The system aims to improve security, privacy, and efficiency in the management of patients requiring different levels of care. The fundamentals of RFID technology, system components, software architecture, and the technical specifications of each hardware element—such as the battery, voltage converter modules, RDM6300 RFID reader, HC-05 Bluetooth module, and RFID card—are presented. Additionally, the software architecture includes the use of XAMPP for the MySQL database and a web interface for data management, and MIT App Inventor for mobile application development. A key feature of the project is the integration of RFID technology into clothing, demonstrated by a prototype T-shirt with a hidden pocket for the RFID card, ensuring discretion and comfort. The preliminary results (without patient testing) demonstrate the viability and effectiveness of the proposed solution in accurately and discreetly identifying patients, contributing to a safer and more controlled care environment.

Keywords — RFID, Patient Identification, Monitoring Systems, Smart Clothing.

1. INTRODUCTION

RFID stands for Radio Frequency Identification, a technology that uses radio waves to collect and transfer data, allowing data to be captured efficiently, automatically, and in real time, without human intervention. This technology, alone or in conjunction with other technologies, has been considered a potential solution to reduce problems

that put public health at risk or to improve its management [1].

The identification process consists of reading an RFID tag applied to an asset or person without any physical contact. The advantage is that an RFID reader can read multiple tags simultaneously at a greater distance and, therefore, without the need to approach the reader, unlike traditional barcode reading, commonly used on wristbands. Therefore, it is possible to assign an electronic tag to assets, healthcare professionals, or patients, which, once tagged, can be identified, tracked, and managed through a centralized database using widespread IT (Information Technology) devices such as PDAs (Personal Digital Assistants) or cell phones [2, 3].

RFID tags, also known as transponders (transmitter + responder), have an internal mechanism for storing data (microchip) and another for communicating that data (antenna). Basically, RFID technology works as follows: the reader, using electromagnetic waves, energizes the tag, which responds by transmitting its identification code. The reader receives this code and makes it available to middleware (final software), which defines the purpose of the received data. The idealized system is shown in Figure 1. Choosing the right RFID tag for a project depends on factors such as memory capacity, tag rating, and operating frequency.

Fig. 1 Idealized system

Source: Available at: <https://www.telefieldrfid.com/rfid-the-basics-you-need-to-know/>

Correct patient identification is essential for healthcare safety in hospitals, clinics, and offices. To maintain patient well-being and ensure safety, the World Health Organization (WHO) created the International Patient Safety Goals in 2004. The first goal is precisely the International Patient Safety Goal adopted by health organizations around the world [4, 5].

Historically, identification methods in healthcare institutions have relied on manual systems, such as paper records, identification tags, and, most importantly, identification bracelets. However, wristbands can have some drawbacks, such as loss, difficulty reading, or accidental or intentional removal by the patient, which can compromise security.

To address these challenges and increase security, new technologies have been adopted. Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) appears as an innovative solution, allowing the automatic tracking and identification of both patients and hospital equipment [6].

These new technologies aim to improve reliability in patient identification, contributing to safer and more effective healthcare.

To overcome the problem of identifying less collaborative patients, cases in which the patient has some type of disability, a partnership was established between the Federal Technological University of Paraná (UTFPR - Curitiba) and the Pequeno Cotelengo Healthcare Complex, located in Curitiba - PR, as an Extension Project, to develop a new Patient Identification system.

This partnership promotes the application of technological knowledge to improve the quality of life of those sheltered and provides an environment for learning and growth for UTFPR and UFPR students.

Cotelengo Health Complex welcomes and serves people with multiple disabilities who are at risk, abandoned by their families, and hospital residents. Residents receive comprehensive care, including shelter, food, medical care, rehabilitation, and special education.

UTFPR seeks excellence in technological education, interacting ethically, sustainably, productively, and innovatively with the community, with the aim of promoting knowledge and society.

The main objective of this extension project was to determine the best way to identify the patient in order to reduce the occurrence of incidents/accidents, track information related to the patient's condition, and also providing the location of the patient within the Institution.

The partnership between UTFPR and the Pequeno Cotelengo Healthcare Complex exemplifies the practical and humanitarian application of technological education, contributing to social development and the advancement of knowledge in society.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

To develop the system, a technical visit and in-depth analysis and segmentation of the types of patients housed at the institution (Pequeno Cotelengo Healthcare Complex) were conducted, aiming to understand their specific needs and optimize the project. As the institution's team pointed out, the level of care required by patients varies considerably depending on the severity of their mental and physical health conditions, and there are different sectors within the complex where these groups of patients are allocated.

Based on the segmentation of patient profiles, different alternatives for integrating the RFID card into their daily lives were identified and evaluated (e.g., a card attached to a lanyard around the neck, a card in a coat/vest pocket, or even sewing the card into a piece of clothing). The use of a lanyard and pocket would be appropriate for less hostile patients, while sewing would be a first alternative for more resistant patients with more hostile behavior.

The construction of the prototype involved the integration of several electronic components, selected based on their functionality, cost-benefit and suitability to the application environment, as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 Prototype configuration
Source: Authors' collection

For the prototype, a card with a Serial RS-232 format was chosen, which is a communication standard between electronic devices. In the project, the RFID reader communicates with the card via an RS-232 interface, allowing the exchange of identification information. For identification, the card was positioned on the sleeve of a shirt (Figure 3).

III. RESULTS

Fig. 3 Graphic representation of the t-shirt with embroidery and internal pocket for inserting the card
Source: Source: Authors' collection

The circuit assembly was initially carried out on a protoboard for testing and validating the connections (Figure 4).

Fig. 4 Assembling the circuit on the breadboard
Source: Source: Authors' collection

Software was also created to store patient data. For this project, XAMPP, installed on Windows 11, was chosen to run the services required for communication between the prototype, the database, and the mobile application.

System software architecture was developed to allow management of patient data and interaction with the hardware prototype, ensuring accessibility and security.

The mobile application developed serves as the primary interface for the care team, allowing them to read RFID card data and query associated information from the database.

Figure 5 shows the Patient Identifier prototype. The components were hot-glued to a black plastic box to make the prototype portable.

Fig. 5 Box containing all prototype elements
Source: Source: Authors' collection

Figure 6 shows the integration of the suggested card and the Patient Identifier, containing the symbol to define the location of the receiving antenna.

Aligning the card with the reader antenna, facilitated by the silkscreen on the prototype box lid, proved effective in obtaining accurate readings.

Fig. 6 - Prototype showing card alignment with the antenna.
Source: Authors' collection

The card purchased for prototype testing, from the manufacturer Intelbras, is compatible with this project.

As a suggestion, a mark was made on the clothing (embroidery), with the Institution's logo (Figure 7A), in the exact size of the card, to make it easier to find for whoever

uses the prototype and Figure 7B shows how to insert the card into the shirt.

Fig. 7 A) T-shirt prototype and B) Card placement in the T-shirt.
Source: Authors' collection

Marking the patient's clothing with the institution's logo and the exact size of the card is a practical improvement that can improve usability in a real-world environment, ensuring ideal positioning for reading the RF signal, as well as keeping the reading card out of reach of attendees.

Furthermore, as a result, a database called *Cotolengo* was created (Figure 8) and within it a table with records of those assisted, containing the following data:

cod	1300670996	130066A86D	150039ED11	1300669A05
apelido	Tigresa	Fera	Raio de Sol	Canarinho
nome	Ana Luiza Oliveira	Rafael Santos	Isabela Rodrigues	Gabriel Costa
prontuario	98765432	24681357	13579246	36925814
nascimento	03/07/1972	15/09/1957	02/11/2008	18/05/1997
nome_mae	Maria Oliveira	Renata Santos	Fernanda Rodrigues	Carla Costa
setor	Casas Lares	Lar Sao Francisco	Lar Santa Teresinha	Lar Divina Providencia
leito	102A	215B	307C	412D
foto				
cod_barras				

Fig. 8 Database
Source: Source: Authors' collection

Using our mobile application, it enabled efficient recording and consultation of patient information.

The results achieved with the creation of the prototype and the combination of hardware and software systems show that it is possible to use RFID technology to identify patients discreetly, safely and effectively in special care environments.

The portable prototype (RFID and Bluetooth reader), protected by a plastic box, allows the care team to approach the patient for quick identification, without needing to interact directly with them.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper described the creation of an RFID-based Patient Identification system designed to meet the unique demands of special care settings such as the Pequeno Cotelengo Healthcare Complex.

The possibility of combining low-cost hardware components, such as the RDM6300 RFID reader and the HC-05 Bluetooth module, with an independent battery and a voltage converter, to develop a portable reading device was demonstrated.

MySQL database managed through XAMPP and a web interface, as well as a mobile application created enabled efficient recording and retrieval of patient information.

The next steps will be to approve the project in an Ethics Committee involving Human Beings to be able to carry out tests in a real environment.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Authors thank to Pequeno Cotelengo Healthcare Complex, PPGEB-UTFPR Curitiba and MEI-U UTFPR Curitiba.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Profetto, L., Gherardelli, M. & Iadanza, E. Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) in healthcare: where are we? A scoping review. *Health Technol.* 12, 879–891 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12553-022-00696-1>

2. Yao, W., Chu, CH. & Li, Z. The Adoption and Implementation of RFID Technologies in Healthcare: A Literature Review. *J Med Syst* 36, 3507–3525 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10916-011-9789-8>
3. Kolokathi A, Rallis P. Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) in healthcare: a literature review. *Stud Health Technol Inform.* 2013 ;190:157 -9. PMID: 23823408.
4. World Health Organization [WHO]. (2007). *Patient Safety: Global Patient Safety Challenge: Safe Surgery Saves Lives.* Geneva: WHO.
5. The Joint Commission. (2020). *National Patient Safety Goals for Hospitals, Effective January 1, 2020.* Oakbrook Terrace, IL: The Joint Commission.
6. Ahd Abugabah , Ahmad AL Smadi , Luke Houghton. RFID in Health care: A review of the real-world application in hospitals, *Procedia Computer Science*, Volume 220, 2023, Pages 8-15, ISSN 1877-0509, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2023.03.004> .

Enter the information of the corresponding author:

Author : Frieda Saicla Barros
Institute: UTFPR Curitiba
Street: Av. Sete de Setembro, 3165
City: Curitiba-PR
Country: Brazil
Email: saicla@utfpr.edu.br